

USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH

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Annotation: In the language field, the purpose of a foreign language teaching in the communication method is to teach communication in oral and written form within the framework of a speech situation. It is well known that speaking is the way to communicate orally. The aim of the language training in higher educational institution is to develop the ability to communicate orally in a variety of situations according to the real needs and interests of the students.

Key words: conversation, oral communication, speech, essential, skills, competency, significant, knowledge.

Oral communication skills are fundamental to the development of literacy and essential for thinking and learning. It includes individuals conversing with each other, be it direct conversation or telephonic conversation. Speeches, presentations, discussions are all forms of oral communication. One of the benefits of developing oral communication skills is that students can develop competency in something that is very pervasive in their lives — to reflect on it, to practice it, to get feedback on it so that they can become better at accomplishing their goals. In order to facilitate communication, we need to take into account the specific characteristics of this type of speech activity, such as motivation, purposefulness, activity, connection with a person's personality and thinking activity, independent skills. If there are goals and motives of communication, taking into account the specific features of the participants of communication, their age, level of development, the act of communication within the framework of a speech situation will certainly take place.

To create these conditions in the process of learning English, methods of activation can be used, which take into account all the above features of oral speech activity.

Advantages of these methods are that the students, actively participating in the learning process, begin to think, remember, use the acquired language material. Through conversation students not only communicate information but also explore and come to understand ideas and concepts; identify and solve problems; organize their experience and knowledge, express and clarify their thoughts, feelings, and opinions. Listening and speaking skills are essential for interaction at home, at school, and in the community.

Oral communication is generally recommended when the communication matter is of temporary kind or where a direct interaction is required. Face to face communication is significant so as to build a rapport and trust.

Advantages of Oral Communication

- There is high level of understanding and transparency in oral communication as it is interpersonal.
- There is no element of rigidity in oral communication. There is flexibility for allowing changes in the decisions previously taken.
- The feedback is spontaneous in case of oral communication. Thus, decisions can be made quickly without any delay.
- Oral communication is not only time saving, but it also saves upon money and efforts.
- Oral communication is best in case of problem resolution. The conflicts, disputes and many issues/differences can be put to an end by talking them over.
- Oral communication is an essential for teamwork and group energy.
- Oral communication promotes a receptive and encouraging morale among organizational employees.
- Oral communication can be best used to transfer private and confidential information/matter.

Disadvantages/Limitations of Oral Communication

- Relying only on oral communication may not be sufficient as business communication is formal and very organized.
- Oral communication is less authentic than written communication as they are informal and not as organized as written communication.
- Oral communication is time-saving as far as daily interactions are concerned, but in case of meetings, long speeches consume lot of time and are unproductive at times.
- Oral communications are not easy to maintain and thus they are unsteady.
- There may be misunderstandings as the information is not complete and may lack essentials.
- It requires attentiveness and great receptivity on part of the receivers/audience.
- Oral communication is not frequently used as legal records except in investigation work.

This technique promotes interaction between the participants of the educational process is interactive. The teacher is equal among equals when using these techniques in the classroom: he can ask questions, offer answers, make assumptions, express his opinion, raising interest and motivation of students.

Conclusion: Interactive methods are a useful and fruitful component in teaching a foreign language, due to their inherent advantages in developing communicative, cognitive, creative abilities of students, and also due to the possibility to form students' continual interest in the foreign language culture of the country under consideration.

To achieve success in teaching-learning process a special lesson pattern was developed. The interactive method-based teaching pattern, suggested in the article, increased young learners' motivation, broadened their horizon, helped to create comfortable educational environment and resulted in their ability to work independently and think critically. Today communication can be seen as describing

a set of core principles about language learning and teaching, as summarized above, assumptions which can be applied in different ways and which address different aspects of the processes of teaching and learning.

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